

STUDY OF RADIOACTIVE POLLUTION: A GLOBBAL HAZARDS FOR LIFE AND NATURE

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Introduction

Radiation is the emission of particle or energy in wave form. This is stated as electromagnetic radiation. Examples consist of: visible light, radio waves, microwaves, infrared and ultraviolet lights, X-rays, and gamma-rays [1]. Radiation can be described as two basic types, ionizing and non-ionizing radiation. The discussion will include a **review** of radiation of radioactivity. There are three main kinds of ionizing radiation which are included alpha particles, beta particles and gamma rays. Beside these there forms of ionizing also we have neutrons, protons, heavy charged particles, X-ray and others. Radioactive substance can penetrate into the body by inhalation, ingestion or dermal absorption. In addition, gamma radiation external to the body can enter the skin and produce a dose various tissue [2]. Non ionizing radiation refers to radioactive energy which as opposed to produce charged ions when passing through matters has enough energy only for excitation. However it is known to cause biological effects. Non ionizing radiations usually work together with tissue through the generation of heat. The hazard depends on the ability to go through the human body and the absorption characteristics of different tissues [3].

In this article we will discuss about the radiations which are the cause of radioactive pollution. These radiations are emitted by radioactive decay of unstable heavy atoms nuclei. Exposure of these radiations can cause damage to living cells and environment. Concern for radioactive pollution increased after the discovery of artificial radioactivity, development of
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nuclear weapons and installation of nuclear reactors for generating electricity. We shall discuss the possible threat to human health and environment due to nuclear radiations both from natural and anthropogenic (man-made) sources. Radioactive waste, arising from civilian nuclear activities as well as from defence-related nuclear-weapon activities, poses a formidable problem for handling and protecting the environment to be safe to the present and future generations.

This communication deals with this global problem in its varied aspects and discusses the cause for concern, the magnitude of the waste involved and various solutions proposed and being practised. As nuclear power and arsenal grow, continuous monitoring and immobilization of the waste over several decades and centuries and deposition in safe repositories, assumes great relevance and importance [4]. Methods for the safe disposal of nuclear waste materials will also be discussed. This method is the state-of-the-art in nuclear waste disposal technology. It is the single viable means of disposing radioactive waste that ensures non return of the relegated material to the biosphere. At the same time, it affords inaccessibility to eliminated weapons material. The principle involved is the removal of the material from the biosphere faster than it can return. It is considered that the safest, the most sensible, the most economical, the most stable long-term, the most environmentally benign, the most utterly obvious places to get rid of nuclear waste, high-level waste or low-level waste is in the deep oceans that cover 70% of the planet [5].

Keywords- Radioactivity, Radioactive pollution, Alpha, Beta particles. Nuclear explosions, Cell destruction etc.

WHAT IS RADIOACTIVE POLLUTION?

Radioactive pollution is the presence of harmful substances emitting radiation in the environment, they are dangerous to the ecosystem and living organisms. This radiation is a form of energy that is released from the nuclei of the atoms in the radioactive material and these cause harm to plants, animals and even humans. It can cause damage to the living cells and cause diseases like cancer. Radioactive pollution begins when radioactive substances are excessively present in the environment like in air, water or soil. A few examples of radioactive elements are Uranium, Thorium, and Plutonium.

Example of radioactive pollution:

One of the most infamous cases that resulted in radioactive pollution was the Chernobyl disaster. Other examples include:

- a. **Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Disaster:** Following a major earthquake, a 15-meter tsunami disabled the power supply and cooling of three Fukushima Daiichi reactors, causing a nuclear accident beginning on 11 March 2011. All three cores largely melted in the first three days. Nobody died as a direct result of the Fukushima nuclear disaster. However, in 2018 one worker in charge of measuring radiation at the plant died of lung cancer caused by radiation exposure. In addition, there have been more than 2,000 disaster-related deaths.
- b. **Nuclear fallout (after atmospheric nuclear explosions):** What happened to the nuclear fallout after the explosion. The Chernobyl disaster was a nuclear accident that occurred on 26 April 1986 at the No.4 reactor in the Chernobyl Nuclear Power plant, near the city of Pripyat in the north of the Ukrainian SSR in the Soviet Union. Radioactive material from the nuclear device mixes with the vaporized material in the mushroom cloud. As this vaporized radioactive material cools, it becomes condensed and forms particles, such as dust. The condensed radioactive material then falls back to the earth; this is what is known as fallout. The official death toll directly attributed to Chernobyl that is recognized by the international community is just 31 people with the UN saying it could be 50. However, hundreds of thousands of “liquidators” were sent in to put out the fire at the nuclear power plant and clean up the Chernobyl site afterwards.
- c. **Nuclear attack:** The two bombings killed between 129,000 and 226,000 people, most of whom were civilians, and remain the only use of nuclear weapons in an armed conflict. Japansurrendered to the Allies on 15 August, six days after the bombing of Nagasaki and the Soviet Union’s declaration of war against Japan.

Radioactivity and Radiation

The atom is the building block of matter; it consists of a small massive nucleus surrounded by a cloud of electrons. The nucleus is composed of positively charged protons and neutrally charged neutrons [6]. If the nucleus contains either excess neutrons or protons, the forces between these constituents will be unbalanced, leading to an unstable nucleus. An unstable nucleus will continually vibrate and will attempt to reach stability by undergoing radioactive decay. The major types of radiation emitted during radioactive decay include alpha particles, beta particles, gamma rays, and neutron radiation [7].

1. Alpha Particles (α): Alpha particles are energetic and positively charged helium nuclei consisting of two protons and two neutrons. The emission of these particles is comparatively rare in nuclides lighter than lead, but it is common for the heavier nuclides such as uranium-

238, radium-226, and polonium-210. Even though these particles are highly energetic, their high mass leads to slow propagation through air, and they can be absorbed completely by paper or skin.

2. Beta Particles (β): Beta particles are fast-moving electrons emitted from the nucleus during radioactive decay. Two forms of beta decays exist. In the first, $+\beta$ decay, one proton is transformed into a neutron and a positron and neutrino are emitted. In the second, $-\beta$ decay, a neutron change into a proton and antineutrino are emitted. Human beings are exposed to beta particles from both artificial and natural radiation sources. Common radionuclides that produce significant beta radiation include tritium, carbon-14, and strontium-90. Beta particles are more penetrating than alpha particles: they can be completely absorbed by sheets of plastic, glass, or metal. However, beta radiation is less damaging over equally traveled distances.

3. Gamma Rays (γ): Gamma rays are weightless packets of energy called photons, a form of high-frequency electromagnetic radiation. One source of gamma rays in the environment is naturally occurring potassium-40, which is present in the human body. Artificial sources include cobalt-60 and cesium-137. Gamma rays are very penetrating and only dense materials such as lead can provide good shielding from them. Gamma rays can easily pass completely through the human body, with only a fraction absorbed by tissue.

4. Neutron Radiation (n): Neutron radiation is a neutron emitted by an unstable nucleus, often fission and fusion. Neutrons are highly penetrating; when they interact with matter or tissue, they cause the emission of β and γ radiations.

RADIATION NATURE & TYPE

Radiation is energy travelling through space. Energy can be transported either in form of electromagnetic waves (radiations) or a stream of energetic particles, which can be electrically charged or neutral.

These radiations are of two types:

1. Non-ionizing radiations: These are electromagnetic waves of longer wave length from near ultraviolet rays to radio waves. These do not have enough energy to ionize them.

2. Ionizing radiations: These are electromagnetic radiations having high energy, such as short wave length ultra violet radiations, X-rays and gamma rays. The energetic rays produced in radioactive decay can cause ionization of atoms and molecules of the medium through which they pass and convert them charged ions.

Radiations are gamma, beta, alpha produced by the process called radioactive decay. It can affect other non-radioactive atoms to become radioactive and give out radioactive radiations.

RADIOACTIVE POLLUTION & THEIR SOURCES

Living organisms are continuously exposed to a variety of radiations called background radiations. If the level of the radioactive radiations increases above a certain limit it causes harmful effects to living beings. This harmful level of radiations emitted by radioactive elements is called radioactive pollution. There are two types of sources [8].

1. Natural sources

(i) Cosmic rays:

Cosmic radiation is produced when solar and galactic cosmic radiations collide with atoms of air (oxygen, nitrogen, and hydrogen) in the upper layers of the atmosphere to generate a complex set of secondary charged and uncharged particles, including protons, neutrons, pions, and lower-Z nuclei. These secondary particles generate more nucleons, producing a nucleonic cascade in the atmosphere. **Figure 1** presents the contribution to dose equivalent rate from different cosmic ray components as a function of altitude[9]. From this figure, it is clear that at low altitude, muons represent the main source for exposure. As the altitude increases, the radiation exposure will be mainly due to neutrons, electrons/photons, and protons.

Figure 1. Components of the Dose Equivalent Rate Form Cosmic Rays in the Atmosphere.9

(ii) Terrestrial radiation:

Terrestrial radiation is emitted by natural radioactive atoms present in natural materials such as soil, rocks, and clay. The predominant radioactive atoms in these materials include uranium, thorium, radium, and potassium. The decay of radium generates radon, a radioactive gas that is a high contributor to the overall terrestrial dose for many people [10]. When the building material or the surrounding soils contain radium, radon gas produced from the radium can accumulate in the home; for homes with low air ventilation radon concentrations can be high and lead to significant radiation exposures [11]. There are regions around the world where the concentrations of thorium, uranium, and other natural radionuclides in soil and beach sand exceed the average background levels by large margins. As examples, in the Brazilian coastal town of Guarapari and along the Kerala coast in India, the personal annual doses of members of the public may exceed the occupational annual dose limit of 20 mSv because of high levels of uranium and thorium in the local geology [12–15].

2. Man-Made sources

(i) Medical sources: The nuclear radiations are used for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes. The X-rays are used in radiology and CT scan for medical purposes, and gamma rays for treatment of cancer. The exposure to radiations during these applications causes radioactive pollution.

(ii). Nuclear explosions: The nuclear explosions are very hazardous to living beings and critical sources of nuclear radiations, e.g., effects of atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan during II world war.

(iii). Nuclear wastes: Nuclear reactors used for producing electricity require large amount of water to act as coolant medium. Once used, this coolant water containing small amount of radioactive substances (nuclear waste) is released into river or sea, thus polluting the water bodies.

(iv). Nuclear material processing: Reprocessing of spent nuclear fuels produces Pollution in the environment.

(v). Nuclear power plants: Radiations may leak from nuclear power plants/nuclear reactors. It is often feared that even with the best design and techniques, and proper handling, some radiations are routinely released into the air and water.

Effects of radioactive pollution

1. Genetic mutation:

Radiation has adverse effects when it comes to genetics. It leads to damage of DNA strands leading to genetic break up in the course of time. The degree of genetic mutation leading to changes in DNA composition vary due to the level of radiation one has been exposed to and kind of exposure.

In the event that a human or an animal is exposed to too much radiation from the atmosphere, food consumed and even water used then chances are that their bodies have already absorbed the radiation, Once in body, it remains active because energy cannot be destroyed.

2. **Diseases:** Cancer is the most dominant radiation related disease. It has developed over the years and poses great risk in global health. Other include leukemia, anemia, hemorrhage, s reduction in the life span leading to premature aging and premature death as well as other such as cardiovascular complication. Leukemia for instance is caused by radiation in the bone marrow.
3. **Soil infertility:** Radioactive matter is present in the soil, either due to nuclear waste dumps or naturally affecting the soil. It reacts with the nutrients found in soil and makes destructive compounds that harm the fertility of the soil, thereby making it infertile. It also makes the soil toxic and unfit for use. The crops harvested in the soil are riddled with radiation, thus making them unfit for consumption by human and animals.
4. **Cell destruction:** Radioactive pollution has diverse effects such as the alteration of cells. The bodies of living organisms are unique in that there are millions of cells in one single body, where each has its purpose to fulfil. Radiation distorts the cells present leading to permanent damage of the various organs and organ system. In the face of too much radiation, permanent illnesses and death are inevitable.
5. **Burns:** You might not be able to feel the radiation penetrating your skin, but it can be observed by the burns it causes on the body. Not only burns but red lesions and sores also are proof of radioactive burns.

Prevention of radioactive pollution

- Prevention of radioactive pollution is a challenge, but some practical measures can be followed. The following are the ways by which radioactive pollution can be prevented:
- One must ensure the safety and management of radioactive materials in nuclear stations and research laboratories.

- One must follow the dress code and practices to ensure safety in nuclear station while handling radioactive material.
- Safe disposal of radioactive material is must and this procedure should be followed.
- One must be aware of the emission of waste and minimize the risk of environmental contamination by radioactive materials.
- The public should also be made aware of the impact and risk of radioactive pollution.

Conclusion

Radioactive elements affect the environment and can cause a risk to human health if inhaled, injected or exposed. Human tissues absorb radiation through polluted water and foodstuff, which can cause serious health risks. High radiation exposures can result in acute radiation syndrome or cutaneous radiation damage. Exposure to radiation causes various disorders in human physiology.

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